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SELECTION OF COST DRIVERS IN ACTIVITY BASED COSTING WITH FUZZY GENETIC ALGORITHMS (PAPER FOR DEBATE)

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In such a situation it becomes necessary, on the one hand, to set up mechanisms allowing complex problems to be handled, the line being taken in this paper that for such purposes genetic algorithms are of use. On the other hand, it is important to enable their application jointly with tools that permit uncertain information to be dealt with, which in its turn justifies interest in the Theory of Fuzzy Sets that can operate with this type of information.

Hence, this paper presents a Fuzzy Genetic Algorithm as a mechanism facilitating the process of selection of cost drivers in ABC systems in which it is necessary to aggregate or lump together activities.

SELECTION OF COST DRIVERS IN ABC WITH FUZZY GENETIC ALGORITHMS

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Abstract

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In such a situation it becomes necessary, on the one hand, to set up mechanisms allowing complex problems to be handled, the line being taken in this paper that for such purposes genetic algorithms are of use. On the other hand, it is important to enable their application jointly with tools that permit uncertain information to be dealt with, which in its turn justifies interest in the Theory of Fuzzy Sets that can operate with this type of information.

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Keywords: Activity Based Costing, Cost Drivers, Uncertainty, Soft Computing Application and Genetic Algorithms

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional cost systems were developed on the basis of an industrial model, in which the information supplied by the systems matched the competitive philosophy dominant in the market, having as its fundamental mantra the need to "beat competitors on costs". This philosophy for competition reinforced the idea of control of unit cost by means of specialization and division of labour, on the basis of a belief that profitability comes from economies of scale and of high-volume business. In such an environment, cost management was synonymous with managing competitiveness and achieving profits, but nowadays this is no longer fully the case.

The changes that have taken place in the competitive environment demand a broader perspective, in which currently relevant factors that are not directly linked to costs would be reflected. In fact, traditional systems have not kept up with the technological evolution in production processes, nor are they in tune with the present-day environment of competition and productivity. The cost management system needs to be reorientated from the viewpoint of recording and analysis after the event towards a mechanism acting in advance on the activities that generate costs.

It is precisely Activity Based Costing (ABC) that has been proposed as a response to the requirements mentioned above. In many circles it is considered capable of helping to eliminate the principal distortions arising in traditional cost accounting.

One of the fundamental aspects of the setting up of an ABC system, besides identifying activities, is the selection of cost drivers that will serve as a vehicle directing costs from the consumption of resources by activities to the final cost bearers, so that these will be ultimately responsible for the greater precision of the system. However, in the literature on this matter there is scarcely any discussion of procedures for designating them, or even any methodology to aid in their identification, selection and control.

In the practical implementation of an ABC system the additional problem arises of the large number of activities carried out within a business, such that it is not economically viable to use a cost driver for each activity. For this reason, many activities have to be lumped together, in a search for a single driver that could be used to impute the costs of all of them to products. This procedure, while commonly accepted, does introduce distortions into the calculation of the cost of products, so that an inadequate aggregation of activities eliminates the objectivity which is supposed to be a feature of ABC due to recognition of the underlying causal relationships which within a given business link resources consumed and products obtained.

In consequence, the design of an optimum costs model based on activities lies in attaining a number of drivers which it is economical to maintain and which at the same time does not introduce distortions of an unacceptable nature into the calculation of costs.

In the light of the above, the next section first undertakes a brief analysis of the repercussions of Activity Based Costing as a valid method for confronting the limitations noted. To this end, a description of the functioning of this system will be offered. This will allow an acquaintance to be made with the problems appearing in the design of the optimum model, and especially the problem of aggregation of activities and selection of drivers. Similarly, an analysis will be undertaken of the existing tools for aiding in such a selection, which will permit the complexity of the problem to be demonstrated, as also the necessity of establishing mechanisms to allow operation with incomplete information.

It becomes necessary then to consider those instruments that can resolve this type of problems, and to this end the third section evaluates the interest of emerging mechanisms for search and optimization that have proved themselves a solution in such circumstances, with the study concentrating on Genetic Algorithms, describing how they work

and the basic elements composing them, with the aim of seeing how they might contribute to resolution of the problem of selecting cost drivers within an ABC system.

Furthermore, owing to the need to operate with data expressed in approximate terms, a fourth section will give an overview of the Theory of Fuzzy Sets as a useful tool in handling uncertainty and of its possible application to the problem under study.

The fifth section assesses the possibility of implementing a genetic algorithm to facilitate the process of selection of cost drivers, recognizing the possible distortions deriving from the aggregation de activities and also allowing operation with uncertain information.

The sixth and final section presents conclusions arising from the work undertaken.

2. ACTIVITY BASED COSTING

Activity Based Costing (ABC) focuses on business activities as the key element in analyzing the behaviour of costs within organizations, relating the expenditure of resources with the activities and processes under way thanks to these resources.

On these lines, it would be possible to interpret ABC systems as taking to their logical conclusion classic theoretical principles, implicit in cost systems, by attempting to tease out and grasp to the fullest extent the cause-and-effect relationships which in a given business underlie the consumption of resources and the obtaining of products. Such relationships must be solidified into units of measurement and these, as is well known, should fulfil a twofold requirement: they should measure both the consumption of resources occurring and what is supplied to products.

In fact, the central idea of ABC is that the final bearers of costs (products or services) do not consume resources but rather activities, and that it is the latter that directly consume resources. In this way, ABC, as shown in Figure 1, recognizes the causal relation between the cost drivers used and the activities to which they are applied.

Figure 1. Causal relation between the cost drivers and the activities

With an ABC methodology, in consequence, the important thing is not the cost of the product, but the cost of the activities that go into it, so that costs can be assigned to products through the activities necessary for their

production. This is the reason for the prior calculation of the cost of the activities carried out by the business, as indicated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Cost of products in ABC system

Hence, in this new context the relationship between the consumption of resources and the production obtained is significantly broadened, because the concept of production is decoupled from its classic sense, to refer to the output derived from each activity, since this latter is the ultimate cause of costs.

In this way, ABC systems may be seen not so much as an absolute break with traditional cost systems, but more as constituting an extension and deepening of the theoretical approaches present in them. This is a response to new demands posed by current conditions, and to the technological advances that permit implementation of cost systems of such a kind, well able to justify themselves on the basis of cost-benefit testing.

2.1. Functioning of an ABC system

The basic functional schematic for an ABC system is shown in Figure 3, where it may be observed that it is based on the following two stages:

1. The first phase (costing of activities) involves identification of the activities, analysis of the costs to be assigned and distributed to each activity and of the cost drivers for this first level.
2. The second phase (costing of products) comprises identification of the final bearers of costs, the cost groups for activities and the precise cost drivers for this second phase.

Figure 3. Functional schematic for an ABC system

The first stage carries out an attribution of the consumption of resources to activities by means of the utilization of cost drivers. This implies a need to specify activities, establish the costs they incur and select the drivers to be used. Procedures for determining consumption that has taken place prior to its being imputed to activities can be very varied. However, once activities have been recognized, in order to make decisions relating to them it is necessary to set up an adequate basis for measure and control of their execution. This must permit closer identification of activities with the costs they cause, because the intention is to go deeper into the problem with an aim of identifying within the sphere of each concrete activity those factors which in the ultimate instance trigger the consumption of resources.

To pick out these factors cost drivers must be determined. They may be defined as the factor whose occurrence will lead to the cost, this factor hence representing the prime cause at activity level (Brimson, 1991, p. 204).

In any case, it is accepted that cost drivers may significantly influence the execution of the activity itself. They are the ultimate cause triggering costs and may be considered the essence of processes of continuous improvement, since study of their behaviour constitutes the basis for discontinuation or improvement of the activities performed. Such a function was not taken on by the simple cost drivers used traditionally. When the above has been achieved, the first phase is deemed concluded.

During the second phase the arrangements for imputing costs to the final bearers are established. These latter can be products, services, batches of products, product or service lines, parts, customers, and so forth, as a function of the needs for information arising in each case.

Imputation of costs to their final bearers is likewise done as a function of the cost drivers selected for each activity, although this does depend on the type of activity in question. The principal classification of activities is the proposal first put forward by Cooper (1990) and later expanded by Cooper and Kaplan (1991). These authors classify activities as of unit level, batch level, product maintenance level and plant maintenance level.

The imputation of costs to products concludes the two principal phases of the basic scheme for operation of an ABC system. The description permits recognition of on of the substantial advantages of this system with respect to other models. This consists of its capacity to make use of a double angle, because it allows information to be obtained about resources, activities and cost bearers (cost dimension) and about the work done by the firm (process dimension), since it incorporates detailed analysis of all the processes (activities) executed.

Nevertheless, despite the advantages that can be gained by using an ABC system, several authors have highlighted the existence of problems with their practical installation. These will be discussed in the next section.

2.2. Problems in the design of the optimum model of ABC system: The selection of cost drivers

It is assumed that an ABC system is capable of providing objective information as long as the range of activities covered in its design goes into as much detail as possible and includes not just those activities involved in the process of manufacture, but also the further activities necessary for the product. However, the level of detail required for this runs counter to other characteristics considered desirable in a cost system, such as being operationally straightforward, simple, and inexpensive.

When it comes to practical applications, the fundamental problem lies in the fact that in general the number of activities is so great that it would be complex, unwieldy and economically unviable to reach the level of detail required. This is both because of what is implied by control and management of so large a number of activities and because of the measurement costs associated with use of a cost driver for every activity. As a result, many activities have to be lumped together as aggregated groups of activities, so that each group can be tracked by a single cost driver. Selection of drivers, particularly the number and type of driver, is converted by this into the principal problem to which an attempt must be made to find an answer when implementing an ABC system.

Thus, determining which will be the cost drivers becomes one of the key aspects of the ABC system, above all in those cases where it is considered necessary to aggregate activities.

In fact, since it is not feasible to lump together only activities which are fully homogenous and perfectly correlated, the objective fixed is the formation of groups of activities of the greatest homogeneity possible and a high degree of correlation.

Consequently, the selection of cost drivers needs to answer two closely linked questions: How many cost drivers should be used? and Which cost drivers should be used?

A. Number of drivers. In respect of the number of drivers required, it seems clear that it will depend on how exact a system is wanted, since the higher the degree of precision, the greater will have to be the number of drivers needed to attain such a level. It would appear prudent to undertake a cost-benefit analysis permitting determination of the threshold at which "precision" starts to push costs beyond an acceptable level.

According to Cooper (1991), three factors may be considered to determine whether a single cost driver is acceptable. These are: diversity in what goes to make up production, costs relative to the activities grouped together and diversity in the volume of production.

a) Diversity in production make-up. Products consuming activities in different proportions are considered divergent products. The impossibility of finding products consuming exactly the same proportion of two different activities means that, owing to this diversity, distortions are always introduced by the lumping together of activities. Hence, the attempt should be to group activities with the smallest degree of divergence possible.

The degree of composition divergence between two products with respect to two activities is measured by calculating the ratio of the two activities consumed by each product and dividing the higher ratio by the lower, so that a degree value of less than one will never occur. The greater the diversity between two products, the greater the distortion that will be caused by using a single driver to impute the costs of these two activities to the products.

b) Costs relating to the activities grouped. The higher the relative cost of an activity, the greater the distortion there will be if an imperfectly correlated cost driver is used to impute the costs of the activity to a product. If there is no divergence between products, this relative cost of activities will not impinge on the grouping together of the activities in question.

c) Diversity in production volumes. This type of diversity is brought about by the fact that volumes of production for different products will vary, owing to the impact of manufacturing batches, of orders, of dispatches, and the like,

which will differ significantly in size. In these circumstances, the choice of drivers for this type of activity must seek the driver that best matches the effect deriving from this difference.

Calculation of the degree of divergence in production volumes is performed by dividing the batch size of the product consuming most activities not linked to volume (high-intensity product), by the batch size of the product consuming the fewest such activities (low-intensity product).

This analysis should be carried out so as to take into account the fact that if there are simultaneous distortions deriving from diversity in volume and in composition, the final effect on costs will depend on the sign and intensity of these deviations, such that all the situations shown in Figure 4 could be envisaged. The combined consideration of the two types of divergence permits a generic listing of situations as indicated in that table.

Div. Volume Div. Make-up	High-intensity	Low-intensity
Large-scale	Compensation: $D_v > D_c$ Excess $D_v < D_c$ Shortfall $D_v = D_c$ Correct	Double for excess
Small-scale	Double for shortfall	Compensation: $D_v > D_c$ Shortfall $D_v < D_c$ Excess $D_v = D_c$ Correct

Figure 4. Simultaneous distortions deriving from diversity in volume and in composition. Final effect

B. Choice of drivers. Once the minimum number of cost drivers required has been established, the next step consists of identifying which are to be used. For this purpose, according to Cooper (1989), the need should be highlighted to take into consideration the following three factors:

a) Measurement cost. In relation to the cost of measurement, an attempt should be made to select those drivers requiring information and data that are relatively easy to collect. Over recent years, computer technology has permitted huge reductions in the cost of measuring many drivers. This reduction has come about in two ways: on the one hand, information required by a large number of drivers is already to hand in firms' information systems; on the other, for a good many drivers the costs of measurement have dropped.

b) Correlation coefficient. The necessity of grouping diverse activities under a limited number of drivers has implicit in it the idea that ABC systems are supported by two fundamental hypotheses, those of homogeneity and proportionality.

- Costs within each of the groupings should be driven by homogenous activities, that is, activities with a high level of correlation.
- Costs for every grouping should be strictly proportional to activity, which means that all the costs for the cost centre ought to vary in proportion to any changes in the level of activity.

Evaluation of how far these hypotheses are fulfilled in each grouping is undertaken by means of an analysis of regression, which will permit identification of those drivers that best match the assumptions.

c) Effects of behaviour. The selection of cost drivers is also shaped by the effect that measurement of them may have on the behaviour of people working in the organization, if individuals feel that their actions will be evaluated in some way related to the cost driver. For this reason, in those situations where this could be possible, drivers should be chosen whose measurement will not affect the work people do.

The three factors noted have an interaction one with another, since each of them can be associated with any of the different costs: cost of measurement, cost of errors and cost of behaviour. The objective must thus be to design a cost system providing the maximum benefit for the minimum cost.

In conclusion, the selection of drivers, owing to the need to group activities in the practical implementation of an ABC system, constitutes the principal problem for which an answer must be sought. It can be seen as a complex problem, as it is a question of attempting to fulfil a range of requirements, among which three stand out in particular:

- a. The choice of drivers must satisfy a set of different and normally incompatible objectives. For instance, a search for precision in the valuations carried out in an ABC system is generally incompatible with the levels of outlay desirable in any cost system.
- b. In the current environment, decisions have to be taken in a short period of time and traditional models for mathematical analysis do not permit such calculations within a reasonable response time.
- c. The information available for taking such decisions is normally incomplete, with uncertainty about data because there is reference to future expectations, so that at best it is possible to have available only information expressed in approximate terms.

These requirements, aimed at establishing an optimum ABC system, can be summed up as needing the implementation of mechanisms permitting resolution of complex problems, with a reasonable response time, and able to make use of imprecise or vague information.

1. Solving a complex problem. To meet the first requisite in the list, there is problem of the selection of drivers, characterized by the multiplicity of objectives and the presence of incompatibilities between the various activities. This implies that the process of grouping them has to be approached with mechanisms of utility in a context of problems of great combinatorial complexity. Consequently, in resolving this question attention must be paid to the possibility of applying search and optimization mechanisms which can successfully handle such circumstances. In this case the choice made was to utilize a Genetic Algorithm.

2. A reasonable response time. The necessity of taking decisions practically in real time makes it essential for the system to be implemented in the shape of some form of computer application with the shortest feasible processing time and in consequence response time.

3. Use of imprecise or vague information. Aggregation of activities to permit selection of a reasonable number of cost drivers is a decision looking into the future, and so the information that it is possible to obtain from it for handling cannot easily be expressed in objective terms. For this reason, a solution of the problem is sought by considering the possibility of using the Theory of Fuzzy Sets as a handy tool for dealing with the uncertainty inherent in the information available.

On the basis of the points raised above, the next section will give a brief description of genetic algorithms, mechanisms for search and optimization that may be of use in the process of aggregating activities in an ABC system with a view to reducing the number of cost drivers used. Thereafter, a description will be set out of the Theory of Fuzzy Sets, so as to provide an acquaintance with the mechanisms it might offer for the resolution of the problem under study.

3. EMERGING SEARCH AND OPTIMIZATION MECHANISMS: GENETIC ALGORITHMS

Genetic algorithms (GAs) are methods based on the genetic processes of living organisms which are used in solving problems of searching and optimization. Their initial development is owed to Holland (1975).

GAs use a direct analogy with natural behaviour, in which the individuals in a population compete among themselves in such a way that those individuals that are most successful in surviving have a greater probability of generating a large number of descendants, while those less endowed give rise to a smaller number of descendants.

The natural behaviour mimicked in GAs presents the following phases, shown in Figure 5. First, a population of individuals is generated, each one representing a feasible solution to the problem that is required to be solved. As a function of the goodness of the solution represented by a given individual, a value is assigned to it that effectively

establishes the degree of efficiency of that individual in competing for certain resources. The better the adaptation of an individual, the greater the probability that that individual will be selected to reproduce itself and, in consequence, that its genetic material will be propagated through successive generations. The process of reproduction is performed by crossing the genetic material of the individual with that of another selected in the same way, generating a new population with better characteristics that replaces the previous one. Thus, over successive generations the new populations will be better adapted than the populations from which they descend. If the GA is correctly constructed, after a reasonable time the population will converge towards an optimum solution for the problem.

Figure 5. Phases of a Genetic Algorithm

The principal advantage of GAs is that they are robust techniques that can be successfully used on a great variety of problems, even in cases where other techniques pose difficulties. Furthermore, while it cannot be guaranteed that a GA will provide the optimum solution, it has been empirically demonstrated that they find acceptable solutions in a time rivalling those of other algorithms for combinatorial optimization.

3.2. Basic elements of a genetic algorithm

A GA starts with a suitable coding or representation of the problem. To determine the goodness of solutions the individuals composing the population represent for the problem to which the algorithm is to be applied, it is necessary to establish an adaptation function to assign a value to each possible solution coded.

Execution of the algorithm consists of selecting the individuals that will act as parents in the process of reproduction, these being bred to generate two offspring on which a mutation operator acts. The result of these

operations will be a set of individuals which represent new possible solutions to the problem and will constitute the next population.

Hence, in order to be able to apply a genetic algorithm the following basic components are required:

- A representation of the potential solutions to the problem.
- A way of creating an initial population of possible solutions.
- An evaluation function to act as an environment, classifying solutions in terms of their "fitness".
- Genetic operators altering the make-up of the offspring produced for the successive generations.
- Values for the various parameters used by the GA, among which should be highlighted population size, probability of breeding, probability of mutations, the number of generations, and the like.

The basic genetic algorithm represents individuals (possible solutions to the problem) by means of a set of parameters equated to genes, these being grouped to constitute a chain of values defined as chromosomes. While there are various arrangements for the codification of individuals, as will be explained below, in general the coding used is mostly based on the binary system $\{0, 1\}$.

The set of parameters representing a particular chromosome is termed a phenotype, and this contains the information required to build an organism, called a genotype. Hence, the fitness of an individual for a problem depends on evaluation of the genotype, which can be inferred from the phenotype, that is, may be computed from the chromosome by means of the evaluation function.

For its part, the evaluation function must be specific for each problem and serves to assign a value to each chromosome separately, this value reflecting the level of adaptation to the problem of the individual represented by the chromosome.

To constitute the next generation of individuals a process of reproduction is carried out. This consists of first selecting the individuals and then submitting them to the crossover operator and producing descendants, which are thereafter subjected to a process of mutation.

The selection of individuals to act as "parents" is normally done randomly. The most widespread procedure is "roulette rank", the aim of which is that the best adapted individuals should be selected.

From the individuals chosen a combination of chromosomes is produced, utilizing principally the operators for crossover and mutation.

•**Crossover operator.** The process of crossing in greatest use is "cross at one point". This involves taking two of the individuals selected as "parents" and cutting their chromosomes at a position chosen at random. In this way, two start and two end segments are produced, and there is a change-over among these to give rise to two new complete chromosomes, as indicated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Crossover operator

•**Mutation operator.** The mutation operator acts de individually on descendants and consists of altering randomly one or more genes from those making up the chromosome, with this being shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Mutation operator

The crossover operator carries out a quicker exploration of the search space and this is usually considered more important than the mutation operator. However, the purpose of the latter is to guarantee that no point within the space being searched can have a zero probability of being examined, which is especially important in ensuring the convergence of the GA.

4. HANDLING UNCERTAINTY: THEORY OF FUZZY SETS

The important characteristics in an ABC system can be grouped under three major headings: precision, effects on behaviour and cost of the system. All depend on the quality and quantity of drivers used. Hence, these models should include and measure all the important factors which are qualitatively or quantitatively measurable, whether they are tangible or intangible.

Traditional mathematics has developed a series of models of use in those cases where all the information necessary is expressed as fixed and certain data. However, these models start to run into difficulties when an attempt is made to bring them close to reality and apply them to situations and problems characterized by constant change and

complexity. The question of being considered here, the grouping of activities for selecting cost drivers, falls into this category.

In an attempt to formalize this phenomenon, the natural tendency to base it on a representation in terms of the certainty of the information available appears to move away from what reality itself demands. In fact, in some research into Management Accounting, under these circumstances resort has been had to stochastic techniques such a supplementary solution in default of others. While these are powerful tools in solving some problems, they lose representational capacity when the information to hand is subject to high levels of subjectivity or vagueness. Their limited capacity to aid in the taking of decisions in turbulent environments has led some authors to suggest applying the Theory of Fuzzy Sets.

Uncertainty, in the context of management in general and of this problem in particular, may be defined as lack of knowledge of the state that will be adopted by a given variable affecting an economic decision, in this case cost drivers. Because of this, different situations have to be contemplated in which it is possible to obtain different results for each feasible course of action. It is not necessarily a question of ignorance, but of its being impossible to establish the probability of all of the states that might be taken on by the variables.

Consequently, if the knowledge to hand of the behaviour of the variables in the model is imprecise, as occurs in the case of the aggregation of activities with the aim of reducing the number of drivers needed, the mathematical technique that should be brought in, in order to facilitate decision taking, must include the notion of level of assumption. Thus, it will be necessary to look to those mathematical tools that permit processing of this information. Fuzzy number were created to reflect the vagueness of human perception and hence the concept of assumption. In this way, the Theory of Fuzzy Sets, as a branch of mathematics concerned with handling both the subjective and the uncertain, constitutes an attempt to capture a phenomenon just as it is in reality and cope with it without trying to make it precise and certain at the price of deforming it to do so (Zadeh, 1965). To the extent that those responsible for managing business organizations recognize that their surroundings and hence the information with which they deal, is uncertain it seems obvious for them to prefer realistic, though imprecise representations as opposed to models which are only supposed to be exact without succeeding in being so.

5. AGGREGATION OF ACTIVITIES FOR THE SELECTION OF COST DRIVERS IN AN ABC SYSTEM BY MEANS OF GENETIC ALGORITHMS WITH UNCERTAIN INFORMATION

In an ABC system an attempt must be made to establish a number of drivers which can be economically maintained, without introducing major distortions into the calculation of the cost of products. This objective implies the aggregation of activities into groups which, while perhaps not permitting an exact calculation of product costs, will facilitate maintenance of the system by providing a workable number of drivers.

The solution sought in this model is the setting up of groups of two activities, minimizing any distortion that might be brought in by aggregation and working out which is the "better" driver of the two for each pair of activities. Additionally, as a function of the cost of measurement for each driver, it will be possible to establish the degree of aggregation that is significant in every specific case.

In view of how important it is to be able to operate with the uncertainty inherent in the variables affecting the decision, the choice was made to work with trapezoidal fuzzy numbers. This was because it is possible to deem a trapezoidal set membership function sufficiently good to capture the imprecision of estimates made as to the values of variables, when in many cases it would be impossible or unnecessary to obtain more accurate valuations.

In addition, with the aim of facilitating explanation of the model, an illustrative example is offered to serve as a basis for developing the various concepts and components of the GA that are being considered in the following sections.

5.1. Setting the problem

The first stage in the practical implementation of an ABC system is an awareness of the activities carried out in the firm and the cost drivers associated with them. On the basis of this information the problem becomes one of deciding how to aggregate activities, and establishing which driver to apply to each group of them.

Let there be a typical firm in which two products (A and B) are manufactured, this involving seven different activities, with the drivers assigned to each of them being as shown in Table 1.

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Driver</i>
<i>Purchases</i>	<i>Number of orders</i>
<i>Reception of materials</i>	<i>Kilograms received</i>
<i>Use of materials</i>	<i>Kilograms consumed</i>
<i>Packing</i>	<i>Containers consumed</i>
<i>Packaging for dispatch</i>	<i>Boxes sold</i>
<i>Loading and unloading</i>	<i>Kilograms supplied</i>
<i>Deliveries</i>	<i>Orders supplied</i>

Table 1. Information of the activities and cost drivers

Information relating to the cost of each activity in future periods can be provided only in the form of an estimate, as it is impossible to determine objectively the outlay on various sorts of consumption of resources that every activity will involve in the future. Nevertheless, the possibility of using estimates will allow an approximation to the cost of each activity, as, for working purposes, is assumed to be expressed by the trapezoidal fuzzy numbers (TFN) given in Table 2.

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Cost (Trapezoidal fuzzy number)</i>
<i>Purchases</i>	<i>[430.000, 440.000, 450.000, 460.000]</i>
<i>Reception of materials</i>	<i>[400.000, 410.000, 415.000, 420.000]</i>
<i>Use of materials</i>	<i>[890.000, 900.000, 915.000, 930.000]</i>
<i>Packing</i>	<i>[2.200.000, 2.220.000, 2.225.000, 2.230.000]</i>
<i>Packaging for dispatch</i>	<i>[1.340.000, 1.345.000, 1.345.000, 1.350.000]</i>
<i>Loading and unloading</i>	<i>[430.000, 430.000, 430.000, 430.000]</i>
<i>Deliveries</i>	<i>[1.250.000, 1.255.000, 1.260.000, 1.260.000]</i>

Table 2. Cost of the activities (TFN)

Thus, for the activity "Purchases", it is expected that the cost will not be less than 430,000 units nor greater than 460,000, with it most likely to be between 440,000 units and 450,000 units. For its part, the cost associated with the activity "Loading and Unloading", on the basis of the data put forward, is recognized as amounting in all probability to 430,000 units.

The reading of the rest of the data utilized in this example of a practical application is to be done in the same way, since in all cases the choice has been for trapezoidal membership functions.

Likewise, the value of each cost driver for all the activities is an uncertain value, but it can be taken as feasible to estimate its amount in approximate terms. For illustrative purposes, the values given in Table 3 are assumed.

<i>Driver</i>	<i>Value (TFN)</i>	
	<i>Product A</i>	<i>Product B</i>
<i>Number of orders</i>	<i>[80, 100, 120, 130]</i>	<i>[50, 55, 55, 60]</i>
<i>Kilograms received</i>	<i>[8.000, 10.000, 12.000, 13.000]</i>	<i>[5.000, 5.500, 6.000, 6.000]</i>
<i>Kilograms consumed</i>	<i>[6.000, 8.000, 10.000, 10.000]</i>	<i>[8.000, 8.500, 8.600, 8.600]</i>
<i>Containers consumed</i>	<i>[120, 130, 140, 150]</i>	<i>[100, 100, 110, 110]</i>
<i>Boxes sold</i>	<i>[100, 110, 110, 120]</i>	<i>[130, 130, 130, 135]</i>
<i>Kilograms supplied</i>	<i>[10.000, 11.000, 11.000, 12.000]</i>	<i>[13.000, 13.000, 13.000, 13.500]</i>
<i>Orders supplied</i>	<i>[200, 210, 220, 230]</i>	<i>[130, 130, 130, 135]</i>

Table 3. Information of the cost drivers (TFN)

In the Table above it is possible to note the estimates made of the drivers for the two products. For instance, the driver "Number of Orders" is expected to be not fewer than 80 nor more than 130 for product A, with its most likely

value lying between 100 and 120 orders. In its turn, for product B the number of orders is expected to be not less than 50 nor more than 60, the greatest probability being for a total of 55.

The screen replicated in Figure 8 shows the previous information in the program implemented in the Visual Basic language, with the purpose of making the model more practical. With this information, it is possible to obtain an estimated value for each of the products, simply by performing the appropriate calculations using fuzzy arithmetic.

Activities	Cost Driver	Cost	Cost	Cost	Cost
Purchases	Number of orders	430.000	440.000	450.000	460.000
Reception of materials	Kilograms received	400.000	410.000	415.000	420.000
Use of materials	Kilograms consumed	890.000	900.000	915.000	930.000
Packing	Containers consumed	2.200.000	2.220.000	2.225.000	2.230.000
Packaging for dispatch	Boxes sold	134.000	134.500	134.500	135.000
Loading and unloading	Kilograms supplied	430.000	430.000	430.000	430.000
Deliveries	Orders supplied	1.250.000	1.255.000	1.260.000	1.260.000

Cost drivers	Product A				Product B			
	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value
Number of orders	80	100	120	130	50	55	55	60
Kilograms received	8.000	10.000	12.000	13.000	5.000	5.500	6.000	6.000
Kilograms consumed	6.000	8.000	10.000	10.000	8.000	8.500	8.600	8.600
Containers consumed	120	130	140	150	100	100	110	110
Boxes sold	100	110	110	120	130	130	130	135
Kilograms supplied	10.000	11.000	11.000	12.000	13.000	13.000	13.000	13.000
Orders supplied	200	210	220	230	130	130	130	135

Figure 8. Screen with information of the activities and cost drivers

The aim is to use a search and optimization mechanism to couple pairs of activities, indicating for every pair what is the most suitable driver and what distortion is introduced by the grouping. For this purpose the proposal was to utilize a genetic algorithm as the method for searching and optimizing the information given. The implementation of this is described next.

5.2. Codification and selection of the initial population

The most generic criterion for coding in GAs is a binary representation, as the "chain of ones and zeros" can be compared to a chromosome-like structure, so maintaining the parallelism with biology. Nonetheless, the favourable qualities of GAs do not depend on the use of this code, so that other types of coding that are more natural in their fit to the problem to which it is desired to apply the technique are sometimes used. In this instance the choice was for a representation in the form of vectors of whole numbers, the vector's length being equal to the number of activities possible (in this example the length of the vector will be seven), and in which each integer represents the number of the activity to be considered in making the decision.

In respect of the selection of the initial population the option was for a random initialization such that as many vectors of random integers would be generated as there were to be individuals in the initial population.

A sample representation of an initial solution for the specific set of numbers being handle here might be given by the following integer vector: $S = (6, 1, 5, 7, 4, 3, 2)$

In operation, the initial solution proposed in the sample of the application would be:

<i>Position</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Activity</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>

The representation given above of the initial solution would imply that activity 1 (Purchases) should be grouped with activity 6 (Loading and Unloading); activity 2 (Reception of materials) would be paired with activity 1 (Purchases), and so forth.

The randomly generated solutions must be subjected to processing to eliminate individuals that represent solutions which are not feasible, since in the process of aggregation the activities must have correspond one to another. For this purpose the algorithm is constrained so that, when it is generating initial solutions, every time it assigns one feature to another it also allocates the reciprocal link, in order for all the activities to be properly coupled.

In the sample, a representation of one feasible initial solution would be as indicated below:

<i>Position</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>
<i>Activity</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>4</i>

This procedure must be repeated for every generation, as the action of the genetic operators may change the position that a given activity occupies in the vector of integers simulating the solution, and hence cause the possibility that a grouping may not be feasible if the order of the vector is followed.

5.3. Fitness function

Measurement of the adequacy of each solution generated, whether in the initial population or in successive iterations, will be given by the distortion introduced into the calculation of the cost of products by the fact that only a single cost driver is in use for each pair of activities grouped together.

To evaluate the impact of aggregation, the cost of products is calculated with imputation of activities to every pair on the basis of each of the two drivers, the smaller of the two distortions thrown up being thereafter chosen as more adequate for the solution. This evaluation is carried out taking into account the diversity in volume and in

composition of each pair of activities for both products. In this way a fuzzy number (\tilde{F}_s) will be obtained and will indicate the goodness of each solution.

Comparison between the goodness of the various solutions obtained was done on the basis of the fuzzy distance (Kaufmann and Gil-Aluja, 1987) defined as follows:

$$d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \int_0^1 (|A^1 - B^1| + |A^2 - B^2|) d\alpha$$

where $[A^1, A^2]$ is the confidence interval of \tilde{A} for a level of assumption α .

5.4. Operators: selection, crossover and mutation

Selection operator. The selection operator permits determination of which chromosomes in the initial population are to go on to form an active part of the reproduction process. The model proposed used a method of selection proportional to fitness, that is a roulette method (Goldberg, 1989), establishing that those individuals of greatest fitness will have the biggest probability of being selected as parents.

Crossover operator. In the GA put forward here the option taken was to use the classic crossover operator, which is one-point cross-breeding. This operator consists of choosing at random a point on the chains representing the individuals selected as "parents", breaking them there, and then swapping the resulting sub-chains.

However, given the mechanism used for coding, the influence of this operator could cause activities to be repeated in descendants, because the part chains exchanged by the parents might contain activities repeated elsewhere in the parental chain to which they are attached. So, the required pairing up of activities means that it is crucial to subject the output of this operator to a procedure permitting the elimination of such dittographies and facilitating grouping of activities.

An example of the functioning of this operator might be as follows:

Given parents

$$S_1 = (2, 3, 4, 1, 7, 6, 5) \quad S_2 = (1, 2, 6, 5, 4, 3, 7)$$

If the point chosen at random for the crossover is the second position on the chain, the exchange of sub-chains by the parents would yield the following offsprings:

$$S_3 = (2, 3, 6, 5, 4, 3, 7) \quad S_4 = (1, 2, 4, 1, 7, 6, 5)$$

It will be noted that the first offspring repeats activity 3 and lack activity 1, while in the second individual activity 3 would be missing and 1. Consequently, by a simple swap of the two activities in the two resultant individuals, both could be brought into a shape conforming to the coding utilized, as shown below:

$$S_3 = (2, 1, 6, 5, 4, 3, 7) \quad S_4 = (3, 2, 4, 1, 7, 6, 5)$$

In this way, after the functioning of the crossover operator two new individuals are produced representing feasible solutions to the problem, even if it is necessary to subject them once again to a comparison with the restrictions established a priori for pairing activities, so as to ensure the viability of these solutions.

Mutation operator. The intention of this operator is to increase the diversity of the set solutions. In the model proposed mutation is at random, combined with an exchange of activities. This means that a position along the chain is chosen at random and, also at random, an activity is picked to move into the position selected. After this operation that activity is present in duplicate and the activity initially at that point no longer appears, so that in order to avoid such an unacceptable duplication the place where the other copy of the activity is has to be located and this repeat version modified to whichever would otherwise be missing.

An example of this operator in use is the following:

$$S_1 = (2, 1, 6, 5, 4, 3, 7)$$

If the point randomly chosen for a mutation is the third position and the characteristic selected is activity 5, the new individual would in principle be represented:

$$S_1 = (2, 1, 5, 5, 4, 3, 7)$$

The new characteristic is present in duplicate while the initial characteristic (6) has disappeared from the representation of the solution. Thus, the place occupied by the repeated characteristic is located and it is changed for 6:

$$S_1 = (2, 1, 5, 6, 4, 3, 7)$$

After this mechanism, the resultant individual must be subjected to the process for handling non-feasible individuals on the basis of the considerations governing pairing set up during the process of coding.

5.5. End or stop criterion in the search for the best solution

In selecting a criterion for bringing execution of the algorithm to an close, the option taken was to establish a number of generations defined by the end user of the model when setting the parameters for its operation.

In order not to lose the good solutions obtained in each generation, the mechanism termed "elitism" (Goldberg, 1989) was introduced. This consists of keeping the best individual in a generation in those which follow until some other individual exceeds it in adequacy for the problem.

The screen shown in Figure 9 displays the interface for inputting the parameters for the genetic algorithm which are user-defined, specifically, the number of individuals, the number of generations and the percentages for the operators of crossover and mutation.

Figure 9. Interface for the genetic algorithm parameters

The operational parameters for the GA used as an illustration were set as the following: number of generations 25, with 10 individuals in each generation, probability of crossover is 50% and probability of mutation 10%.

The screen shown in Figure 10 displays the evolution of the best individual in each generation. It is worth pointing out that owing to the small number of activities considered in the example developed, the GA encountered a good solution in very few iterations, as can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Evolution Graph

Similarly, the screen shown in Figure 11 displays the best solution found in successive iterations. Here it can be seen how the solution proposes establishes a grouping into pairs of the 7 activities of the sample set, indicating the distortion introduced by each of the drivers into the aggregation set up, as also the driver which causes the least distortion for each group.

Figure 11. Better propose solution by the Genetic Algorithm

Special mention should be made of the group formed by the activities "Packaging for Dispatch" and "Loading and Unloading", whose drivers were respectively "Kilograms Supplied" and "Boxes Sold". These had associated with them the same predicted values. Hence in the best solution found these activities are paired, because the distortion introduced by such an aggregation, as can be noted in the solution put forward, is nil.

6. CONCLUSION

The analysis carried out of the Activity Based Costing system (ABC) permitted the conclusion that it can be a valid model for attributing consumption of resources to products. It also allows management of activities and focuses attention on the sources originating added value, the behaviour of costs and the processes of assignment relating to them.

Nevertheless, consideration of the optimum design for a model ABC system made it plain that there is a need to apply mechanisms facilitating the process of aggregation of activities and the selection of the cost driver best suited to each group of activities. On this point, the study undertaken of genetic algorithms as mechanisms for search and optimization valid for complex problems allowed recognition of their usefulness in the problem under consideration. Likewise, in view of the necessity of operating with uncertain information, the involvement of the Theory of Fuzzy Sets served to demonstrate that operation with this sort of information in the problem of selection of cost drivers for an ABC model is feasible if this type of tool is brought to bear.

Finally, a joint application of genetic algorithms and the operational techniques of the Theory of Fuzzy Sets to a specific example permitted a check on the validity of the considerations noted above, and allowed corroboration of their applicability to the problem in question.

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